

MEASUREMENT AND DETECTION SYSTEM FOR GASIFIER

Htet Myo Aung, Wai Phyo Paing, Khant Si Thu
Student, 5th Year, B.C.Tech.
University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Supervised by

Daw Thida Soe

Faculty of Computer Systems and Technologies

University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Abstract. A gasifier is a device designed to convert carbon-based feedstocks, such as biomass, coal or waste, into gaseous fuels. In this system, the wastewater discharged from the gasifier process is purified by passing through a series of filter tanks. The waste product, chaff water, are filtered separately from chaff ash and polluted water. After sorting, the rest of the chaff will be measured. When the chaff reaches a predetermined level, an automated notification message sends to the user, and phone calls. In order to find out the purity of the water that reaches the final water filter tank, the PH level and the Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) levels are measured and display on the LCD screen. And then, water levels are measured to detect the correctness of the water flow in the water tanks and alarm systems are installed. When the specified level of water purification is reached, it will systematically be discharged outside. At the syngas purification stage, the gas content in the gas purification filter are measured and displayed on an LCD. To detect possible fire dangers when the gasifier is operating, a flame sensor is equipped and if a flame is occurred, a warning tone rings with the buzzer.

Keywords: Arduino Uno, water purification, TDS sensor, PH sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, Gas sensor, Flame sensor, GSM module

INTRODUCTION

Water is an essential resource for all forms of life, and access to clean and safe drinking water is a fundamental human need. However, gasifier processes have led to the contamination of water sources, posing significant health risks to communities worldwide. This system represents an advanced approach to measure the purification of water and control the water level and security of gasifier combining with modern technologies. This innovative system enhances the efficiency, reliability, and environmental sustainability of gasification. Automated measurement systems are an essential component for monitoring and controlling the gasification process.

PROBLEM

Gasifier generates wastewater during cooling and cleaning of producer gas. This wastewater contains harmful chemicals which adversely affect the natural stream if disposed off without treatment. By the effect of gasifier effluent on agricultural soil and vegetable production, gasifier wastewater is not suitable for agricultural fields. It inhibits or delay

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

www.ucsh.edu.mm

growth of plants. By utilizing advanced sensors, this system provides accurate and continuous measurements, ensuring optimal operation and safety. This capability makes the gasifier measurement system, a crucial tool for optimizing performance, improving reliability, and ensuring the environmental compliance of gasification systems.

APPROACH

This project is used the ultrasonic sensor and GSM module to notify the rest of the chaff. When the chaff reaches a certain level, the GSM module are used to automatically send a message to the user and make phone calls. PH sensor, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) sensors and LCD display are used to find out the purity of the water. And then, ultrasonic sensor, LEDs and buzzer are applied to detect the correctness of the water flow. By using Ultrasonic sensor and servo motor, systematically discharged the water on outside. To measure the gas content in the gas purification filter, gas sensor and LCD display are used. To detect possible fire dangers, flame sensor and buzzer are applied.

Figure 1: Circuit Diagram of Water Purification Measurement System

Figure 1 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino UNO and other components such as PH sensor, TDS sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, LCD, LEDs and buzzer.

Figure 2: Circuit Diagram of Fire and Gas Detection, Trash and Water Level Measurement

System

Figure 2 is the circuit diagram for the connection of Arduino UNO and other components such as GSM module, Flame sensor, Gas sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, LCD, servo motor and buzzer.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of Water Purification Measurement System

Figure 4: Block Diagram of Fire and Gas Detection, Trash and Water Level Measurement System

Figure 3 illustrates the block diagram for water purification measurement system. In this system, pH sensor, TDS sensor and Ultrasonic sensors are input devices and buzzer, LCD and LEDs are output devices.

Figure 4 illustrates the block diagram for fire and gas detection, trash and water level measurement system. MQ2 gas sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, and flame sensors are input devices. GSM module, servo motor, LCD and buzzer are output devices.

Figure 5: Flow Chart for Water Purification Measurement System

The flow chart for water purification measurement system is shown in Figure 5.

- If water's PH value is < 7 , display on LCD with "Acidic" and, if PH value is > 7 , display on LCD with "Alkaline". When PH value is $= 7$, display on LCD with "Pure water".
- If water's TDS value is ≤ 300 ppm, display on LCD with "Good". If TDS value is between 300ppm and 600ppm, display on LCD with "Fair". If TDS value is greater than 600ppm, display on LCD with "Poor".
- When water level is between 0cm and 5cm, LED green is ON. If water level is between 5cm and 11cm, LED orange is ON. If water level is > 11 cm, LED red is ON and alarm sound.

Figure 6: Flow Chart of Fire and Gas Detection System

Figure 7: Flow Chart of Trash and Water Level Measurement System

The flow chart for fire and gas detection system is shown in Figure 6.

- If fire is detected, buzzer is ON and alarm sound.
- If gas sensor measures gas content, display gas amount on LCD screen.

The flow chart for trash and water level measurement system is shown in Figure 7.

- If water level is ≥ 8 cm, water gate OPEN.
- If chaff level is ≥ 8 cm, make phone call and send message.

RESULTS

The implementation design of the system is shown in Figure 9. For the water purification measuring process, the PH value is displayed on the LCD with an acidic and alkali value, and the TDS value is shown on the LCD with water conditions of fair, good, and poor. In order to indicate the precision of the water flow, a green LED turns on when the water level is low, an orange LED turns on when the water level is medium, and a red LED turns on and an alert sound when the water level is high. When the water level is high, the water gate control opens, allowing water to flow. To measure gas content in the gas purification filter, gas value is displaying at LCD. Phone calls and messages are sent to the user when the chaff reaches a high level. Alert sounds when a fire becomes apparent.

Figure 9: Implementation Design of the System

By making water filter tanks, it has been found that the environmental damage caused by the waste from the gasifier of large rice mills, such as chaff and polluted water, can be maintained and properly disposed of. Automatically sending messages and making phone calls to the user can reduce human effort and time. As the amount of gas content can be known, gas can be regulated as needed. Fire alarm system can help to protect the building and its contents from damage by detecting a fire early and alerting the authorities so that they can respond quickly. Measurement process at the gasifier has proven to be a robust and effective solution for ensuring safe and clean water, contributing positively to both environmental protection and operational efficiency. By using this system, the gasifier's water filter tanks can be built as a better model.

REFERENCES

- [1] Arena U (2012) Process and technological aspects of municipal solid waste gasification. A review. *Waste Manag* 32:625–639.
- [2] International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). "Renewable Energy Technologies: Cost Analysis Series." 2012.
- [3] Kaupp, A. 1982. The gasification characteristics of rice hulls for the generation of electricity and shaft power on a small (530 hp) scale, 1st Int. Prod. Gas Conf., Colombo, Sri Lanka.
- [4] Philippine Statistics Authority. (2019, March 29). Most Filipino Families have Access to Improved Source of Drinking Water (Results from the 2017 Annual Poverty Indicators Survey (APIS) and Water Quality Testing Module) | Philippine Statistics Authority. Retrieved February 1, 2020.
- [5] Prasad, A.N., Mamun, K.A., Islam, F.R., & Haqva, H. (2015, December). Purification Measurement System. Retrieve June 5, 2020.
- [6] Reed, T.B., and Das, A. "Handbook of Biomass Downdraft Gasifier Engine Systems." SERI, 1988.